

THE IN-SITU MATRIX PROPERTIES OF SHORT-FIBRE
REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a model for the deformation behaviour of discontinuously reinforced short-fibre MMC using a micromechanical approach. It is shown that such an approach can be used to model the response of these materials however, the key to such modelling is to employ the correct property data for the in-situ matrix. Differences between the unreinforced and reinforced matrix properties arise through a combination of effects. These include the presence of internal elastic matrix stresses, and the cohibitive effect of the reinforcement on the plastic deformation response of the matrix alloy. It is shown that if these effects are combined with simple micromechanical models the deformation responses of these MMC can be easily understood. In addition by considering the effect of other variables (such as temperature) on these components the behaviour of these MMC can be modelled for a wider range of service conditions.

KEYWORDS: Short fibre composites; Matrix, Aluminium; Strength;
Micromechanics; Residual Stress

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently a number of models have been developed which attempt to calculate the mechanical properties (in particular the strength) of Metal Matrix Composites (MMC). These range from conventional micromechanical models which are usually employed for continuous fibre reinforced MMC, to more complex alloy strength models for particulate reinforced materials. However, between these two extremes of MMC materials lie short-fibre reinforced composites. In some respects these exhibit features of both continuous fibre and particulate reinforced composites, and both types of model have been applied to these materials. Alloy strength models have been employed with some success, however, parameters within these models sometimes begin to lose their direct physical significance. Equally, when Rule-of-Mixtures (ROM) type micromechanical models are employed, criticism is often levelled at these calculations due to their use of material property data which is determined on the uncombined constituents. The latter is particularly important in short-fibre MMC where residual stress effects and modifications to the in-situ plastic deformation response of the matrix would be expected to contribute significantly to the deformation response of the MMC (1). This paper will attempt to show that relatively simple ROM-based models can be used to describe the deformation response of short-fibre MMC if care is taken to employ the correct in-situ matrix properties.

2. RULE OF MIXTURES MICROMECHANICAL MODELS

ROM models essentially describe the deformation response of composites assuming equi-strain in the individual constituents. At any applied strain, the stress supported by the composite is then given by:

$$\sigma_c = V_f \epsilon_c E_f^1 + (1-V_f) \epsilon_c E_m^1 \quad (1)$$

where:

- σ_c is the instantaneous composite stress
- V_f is the volume fraction of fibre
- ϵ_c is the instantaneous composite strain
- E_f^1 and E_m^1 are the instantaneous fibre and matrix moduli

Different stress levels are therefore supported by the fibres and matrix on the basis of the volume fractions of the constituents and their instantaneous moduli. In practice these moduli will be the Youngs Moduli up to the yield point of the composite, however at this point matrix yielding then takes place and the instantaneous matrix modulus will depend on the level of applied strain. The overall stress supported by the composite is then given by:

$$\sigma_c = V_f \epsilon_c E_f + (1-V_f) \sigma_m^1 \quad (2)$$

where: E_f is the Youngs Modulus of the fibre
 σ_m^1 is the instantaneous matrix stress at the composite strain ϵ_c

In the case of unidirectional, discontinuously reinforced composites equation 2 must be modified to account for the lower reinforcing efficiency of the short fibres, and the composite stress is then given by:

$$\sigma_c = V_f \epsilon_c E_f (1-l_c/2l) + (1-V_f) \sigma_m^1 \quad (3)$$

where: l is the length of the discontinuous fibre
 l_c is the critical transfer length in the composite system

In addition in non-aligned fibre composites equation 3 must be further modified to reduce the reinforcing efficiency. The composite stress is thus given by:

$$\sigma_c = CV_f \epsilon_c E_f (1-l_c/2l) + (1-V_f) \sigma_m^1 \quad (4)$$

where C is an empirical parameter describing the inefficiency of reinforcement due to the non-aligned fibre array.

This is the general rule of mixtures equation for short-fibre composites and assuming that E_f and σ_m^1 are known the composite flow stress at any applied strain can be determined. This then allows the prediction of the composite stress-strain curve. The value of σ_m^1 is a complex problem since the matrices of MMC plastically deform and σ_m^1 does not vary as a simple function of strain. The instantaneous value of this parameter is therefore best obtained from the stress-strain curve of the matrix material. Equation 4 exists in a number of forms,

including one which predicts the ultimate strength of the composite. In this case:

$$\sigma_{uc} = CV_f \epsilon_{uf} E_f (1 - l_c/2l) + (1 - V_f) \sigma_m^* \quad (5)$$

where: σ_{uc} is the ultimate strength of the composite
 ϵ_{uf} is the fibre failure strain
 σ_m^* is the matrix flow stress at ϵ_{uf}

This equation is based on a number of assumptions regarding the failure mechanism of the composite. These are that the fibres do not fracture until a unique fracture stress (equivalent to $\epsilon_{uf} E_f$) where they all fracture together, and that such fracture causes plastic overload of the matrix and therefore catastrophic failure of the composite at ϵ_{uf} . This is clearly an oversimplification for pseudo-randomly oriented short-fibres since they exhibit a distribution of fibre failure strains, and exhibit a distribution of instantaneous fibre stresses due to their pseudo-random orientation. The parameter $CV_f \epsilon_{uf} E_f$ therefore only represents some average of the strengthening due to the fibres, and it cannot be assumed that in practice the composite failure strain is equal to ϵ_{uf} . Equation 5 does, however, allow some analysis of the ultimate strength behaviour of these composites.

3. CALCULATED BEHAVIOUR OF PSEUDO-RANDOMLY REINFORCED SHORT-FIBRE MMC

Although equation 5 depends on certain assumptions as to the failure mechanisms, equation 4 does not. It can therefore be used to calculate the stress-strain behaviour of these composites, if the correct strain dependence of σ_m^1 is known for the in-situ matrix. An example of such a calculation is shown in figure 1 for a δ -alumina fibre reinforced Al-4Cu composite. This shows that in this case good agreement between calculated and measured stress-strain curves are obtained if a value of $7/16$ is assumed for the value of C. This is in good agreement with the value of $3/8$ which is widely employed to describe the inefficiency of reinforcement due to non-axial fibre distributions in thin lamellae. Such a fibre distribution is similar to the 2D random distribution in preform infiltrated materials such as this δ -alumina reinforced Al-4Cu composite (2).

The good agreement in figure 1 shows that such a ROM formalism can be used to calculate the stress-strain curves of some composites using the uncombined properties of the fibre and matrix. However, if equation 5 is applied to this composite it predicts the value for σ_{uc} shown in figure 1. This is an underestimate of the true failure stress and is clearly associated with an underestimate of the composite failure strain.

It is not always however, appropriate to apply the ROM formalism using matrix properties determined on the unreinforced alloy. This can be seen by considering composites based on the aluminium alloy 2618A (Al-Cu-Mg). Figure 2 shows the experimentally determined stress-strain curves for this alloy and for a $0.2V_f$ δ -alumina fibre reinforced composite. This figure also contains the calculated stress-strain curve for the composite using the unreinforced matrix alloy stress-strain data. It is clear that in this case there is poor agreement between the observed and calculated curves, and that application of the ROM using the unreinforced matrix properties produces an overestimate of the composite strength. In some alloys the in-situ matrix properties must therefore differ substantially from those of the unreinforced alloy.

4. IN-SITU MATRIX PROPERTIES

There has been much discussion concerning the in-situ properties of MMC matrices with most interest concentrated on the effect of internal stresses which develop in the composite during processing due to the different thermal expansion coefficients of the fibre and matrix (3). These stresses build up inside the composite on cooling below a critical temperature and in ceramic-fibre composites result, at room temperature, in a tensile stress in the matrix. This residual stress is particularly important since it acts additively to any applied stress and results in matrix yielding (and therefore yielding of the composite) at low applied strains/stresses. If the ROM is to be applied to such composites the in-situ properties of the matrices must therefore be considered, including the level of residual stress.

The in-situ properties of the matrix, modified for the presence of residual stress, can be estimated by displacing the matrix alloy stress-strain curve down the applied stress axis by a value equivalent to the average residual tensile stress acting parallel to the direction of applied stress. In the case of the data in figure 2 where

the level of residual stress is unknown, to a first approximation this can be done by displacing the matrix alloy's stress-strain curve until the matrix yield strain is equal to that observed in the composite. If this "new" in-situ matrix stress-strain curve is used to calculate the composite response the result is that shown in figure 3. It is clear that using this 'in-situ' matrix data produces a much improved calculated stress-strain curve. However, the ROM evaluation using matrix data corrected for residual stress now underestimates the behaviour observed in practice. This difference highlights an additional contribution to the in-situ matrix properties. This additional effect can be seen in figure 4 which shows the unreinforced matrix alloy's stress-strain curve and the 'in-situ' curve required to produce good agreement between the calculated and experimental composite curve (both curves in fig 4 are corrected to the same yield strain). It is clear that an additional factor which must be considered is the effect of the fibre array on the work-hardening characteristics of the matrix alloy. Such an effect has been suggested previously in continuous unidirectionally reinforced MMC where it has been explained in terms of both the effect of the residual stress state on glissile dislocations and the presence of dislocation debris generated by the mismatch in thermal expansion coefficients (both of which increase the workhardening rate). Whatever the source, in a 2618A matrix (fig 4) there is a significant increase in work-hardening rate.

It is clear from the above evaluations that ROM formalisms can be used to calculate both the stress-strain curves of these composites and their ultimate strengths if the following constraint is adhered to, ie the ROM must only be applied to the properties of the in-situ matrix. This may appear to reduce the predictive power of the formalism since it seems to require the experimentally determined composite behaviour before the in-situ properties can be deduced, however, the following guidelines can be used to enable the prediction of the composite properties from the unreinforced behaviour. Where there are no residual stresses built into the composite, unreinforced matrix properties can be applied, with a possible correction for an enhanced work-hardening rate. Such a situation applies to the Al-4Cu matrix in figure 1. It is clear that the residual stresses built up in this composite are relatively small (the composite and alloy yield strains are very close to one another) and therefore any residual stresses present do not significantly alter the matrix alloy response. Such behaviour has been found to occur in lower yield strength matrices including commercially pure

aluminium and Al-4Cu. These lower yield strength matrices also have the additional advantage that the modification of their work-hardening rates is relatively low. The present work suggests that little correction is required to the workhardening characteristics of the unreinforced matrix alloy if its yield strength is below ~ 250 MPa. Above this value the rate must be corrected to generate the correct in-situ properties.

5. ELEVATED TEMPERATURE PROPERTIES

The above discussion has considered only the tensile properties of these composites at room temperature, however, a previous paper (5) has attempted to semi-quantitatively evaluate the high temperature response of these materials. This is particularly important since many of the systems which exhibit no strengthening of the composite at room temperature exhibit significant reinforcement at elevated temperatures. This previous paper evaluated such effects in terms of the change in matrix work-hardening rate as the temperature of the composite increased, and this will be further discussed for a material which exhibits no reinforcement of strength above that of the unreinforced matrix at room temperature. Figure 5 illustrates the effect of elevated temperatures on the stress-strain curves of typical matrix alloys. Although illustrated in terms of normalised values, these property changes are consistent with the typical percentage changes observed in aluminium alloys over the temperature range 20 to 200°C. Such changes in matrix properties have a significant effect on the resulting composite properties. Assuming that the failure strains of the composites are only marginally increased over this temperature range, the change in composite strength with temperature can be calculated. However, in such calculations the effect of residual stress must be included since levels which may be present at room temperature cannot be maintained at higher temperatures due to their relaxation. The effect these elevated temperature matrix properties have on the calculated composite strengths is shown in figure 6 for a 0.2 V_f δ -alumina fibre composite. This figure contains curves for composites containing varying levels of constant internal stress. It is clear from figure 6 that all these composites develop reinforcement at elevated temperatures but the transition to reinforcement behaviour depends on the level of residual stress. This figure also contains an additional curve which schematically illustrates the effect of increasing relaxation of internal stress at higher temperatures. Under such conditions the high-

temperature properties are given by data lying on curves of progressively lower internal stress. This implies that increases in the high temperature strengths of these composites have two principal sources, firstly the change in matrix work hardening rate with temperature, and secondly the systematic relaxation of internal stress.

6. SUMMARY

ROM formalisms can be used to calculate both the stress-strain curves and ultimate strengths of short-fibre reinforced MMC if the correct in-situ matrix properties are employed in such calculations. Where no significant residual stresses are built into the composite matrix during processing, and where the yield strength of the matrix alloy is relatively low, the unreinforced matrix alloy properties can be used in place of the in-situ properties. However, where significant residual stresses are present, and where the matrix alloy yield strengths are relatively high, the in-situ stress-strain curves of the unreinforced alloy must be corrected for the presence of residual stress and enhanced work-hardening rates. If all these aspects are correctly considered simple ROM models can then be used to evaluate both the room temperature properties of the composites, and the change in these properties at elevated temperatures.

7. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Comparison of the experimentally determined and calculated stress-strain curves for a $0.2V_f$ short alumina-fibre reinforced Al-4Cu(T6) composite.

Figure 2. Comparison of the experimentally determined and calculated stress-strain curves for a $0.2V_f$ short-alumina fibre reinforced 2618A composite using unreinforced matrix data.

Figure 3. Comparison of the experimentally determined and calculated stress-strain curves for a $0.2V_f$ short-fibre reinforced 2618A composite using in-situ matrix properties.

Figure 4. Comparison of the matrix alloy workhardening rates in unreinforced and reinforced 2618A.

Figure 5. Effect of temperature on the normalised stress-strain curves of a typical aluminium alloy. Key: T/T_m - Homologous temperature, σ_{um}^{20} - the matrix UTS at 20°C.

Figure 6. Effect of temperature on the normalised strength of a $0.2V_f$ short alumina fibre reinforced aluminum alloy.